

Determining Gaps in Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Prevention

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Background

- Catheter-associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI) is a urinary tract infection related to an indwelling urinary catheter (IUC)
- Accounts for 40% of the hospital acquired infections
- Higher risk of with long-term IUC
- Events remain high in project facility Medical Intensive Care Units (MICU)

Costs:
Per event: \$700 to \$2,000/year
U.S.: \$340 billion/year

Morbidity:
Complications (i.e., antibiotic resistance)

Mortality:
13,000 annually

Purpose

Determine gaps between EBP guidelines and current IUC and CAUTI prevention practice in two MICUs.

To identify:

- Underlying causes of CAUTI
- Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats for CAUTI prevention
- Level of awareness, knowledge, and perceptions of CAUTI prevention among health care personnel (HCP)

Methods

Design: QI, Fishbone, SWOT, and TAP surveys
Setting: Two MICU in a 600-bed, level 1 trauma hospital in Southern California
Participants: Convenience Sample of HCP in MICUs
Measure: Frequencies of responses in each category within surveys

SWOT Analysis

Fishbone

Targeted Assessment for Prevention (TAP)

Discussion

- Simultaneous use of diverse assessments helps identify target areas for improvement activities
- CAUTI prevention guidelines are inconsistently implemented
- SWOT identified substantial strengths and opportunities, to build an effective CAUTI prevention program
- Understanding weaknesses and threats helps leaders focus on strategies to overcome barriers
- Fishbone highlighted weaknesses in patient care management otherwise unknown
- Fishbone open-ended responses noted contributing causes of heavy workload, short staffing, and high acuity as additional causes, but did not elicit a clear root cause for CAUTI

Recommendations

- **Physician Champion:** Define champion role, recruit, and train physician champions.
- **Protocol:** Development of two-person for insertion protocol. Explore policy for nurse-driven protocol to increase empowerment.
- **Alerts:** Add stop order alert to EHR. Implementation of standardized reminders for IUC removal to reduce reliance on traditional practices.
- **Staffing:** Assure appropriate staffing for IUC and CAUTI prevention practices and allow for two-person IUC insertion.
- **Education:** Routine and standardized education and skills competency on guidelines-based IUC and CAUTI prevention practices.
- **Evaluation:** Facility-wide gap analysis with immediate feedback to increase awareness and engagement of stakeholders.